

Ionomer-catalyst interaction in catalyst layer for alkaline membrane water electrolysis

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Abstract

Alkaline membrane water electrolysis is gaining attention as a hydrogen production technology combining advantages of the alkaline and proton exchange membrane water electrolysis. To fully utilize potential of this technology, it is necessary to prepare membrane-electrode-assembly characterised by high efficiency and intensity of the electrolysis. One of the vital demands to achieve this target represents establishment of frequent triple-phase boundary. If concentrated liquid electrolyte is used, this boundary occurrence is established due to the ionic conductivity of the electrolyte solution. In the case of diluted liquid electrolyte, in ideal case demineralised water circulating through the cell, task is accomplished by the interactions between catalyst and ionomer fulfilling the role of binder, as well as ion conductor. This review focusses on advances in in the second approach, namely ionomer design, catalyst layer composition and impact of the selected parameters like catalyst to binder ratio, catalyst load and type of membrane-electrode assembly.

Keywords

Alkaline membrane water electrolysis; ionomer; catalyst layer; catalyst-ionomer interaction; triple-phase-boundary

Graphical Abstract

Introduction

In an alkaline membrane water electrolysis (AMWE, membrane here means anion selective membrane), polymer binders — also referred to as ionomers — represent essential component of the membrane electrode assembly (MEA). Their primary functions are at first to enable ionic conduction within the catalyst layer (CL) by facilitating hydroxide ion transport to or from active catalytic sites [1, 2]. At second, they provide CL mechanical cohesion by binding catalyst particles between themselves and to the substrate surface. Binder allows to form a stable, interconnected microstructure of CL with appropriate porosity, water distribution, and gas transport, i.e. factors critical for MEA efficiency and durability [3, 4].

There are two main strategies for incorporating binders in MEA fabrication: Catalyst-Coated Membrane (CCM) and Catalyst-Coated Substrate (CCS). In the CCM approach, CLs are applied directly on to the membrane surface, maximizing the ionic contact between these two components [5]. In the CCS method, the CL is first deposited on a porous electron conductive support and later assembled with the membrane. This approach offers more flexibility in fabrication and well-established electron contact for catalyst particles. At the same time, however, it may introduce additional resistance at the interface with polymer membrane.

While membranes and binders may share similar ionic functionalities, they have different roles and have to satisfy different mechanical requirements. Both components must provide long-term dimensional and chemical stability. On the other hand, binders need to be well processable, adequately adhesive to catalysts, and resist to the mechanical tension caused by evolved gas phase. Because of these differing demands, and different approaches to MEA (CCM or CCS), it is common—and often beneficial—for the binder material to differ from the membrane one in properties.

These differing requirements underscore the importance of selecting or designing binder materials that are specifically suited to the unique conditions of each electrode, i.e. polarity, substrate and catalyst used, rather than employing a one-size-fits-all approach.

Second part of the CL represents catalyst itself. Both parts, ionomer and catalyst must correspondingly interact to form well performing CL. As already mentioned, deposition of the CL represents complex task influenced by several parameters. As main ones, beside materials selection, ratio between catalyst and ionomer load shall be mentioned. It influences performance of the CL due to the tuning of the ratio between electronic and ionic conductivity, as well as mechanical stability. Another parameter represents total catalyst load, which is related to the thickness of the CL, as well as to the mass and charge transport constraints. Of course, the performance of CL is affected by type of the catalyst. Significant differences can be found between catalysts based on platinum group metals (PGM; Pt, Ir, Ru, Pd) and non-platinum group metals (PGM-free; like Ni, Co, Fe, Mn, Mo, Cu).

The aim of this paper is thus to review critically today's knowledge on the research and development of the AMWE CL. This includes information on the types of the commercially available ionomers as well as trends in development of the new materials. In the next part, impact of the ionomer interaction with catalyst is discussed with a special focus on the catalyst to binder ratio, total catalyst load and MEA type.

Commercial ionomers

The common practice represents using ionomer and membrane materials from the same chemical family to optimize MEA integrity and electrochemical performance. For example, the FAA-3 ionomer is commonly paired with the FAA3-50[®] membrane, both produced by FumaTech [6-10]. Similarly, the AS-4 ionomer is used with the A201 membrane, both from Tokuyama. In the case of PiperION, the ionomer and membrane are both derived from poly(aryl piperidinium) structures, offering excellent compatibility and performance in harsh alkaline environments.

As illustrated in the Table S1, commercial polymer binders used in AMWE can be categorized based on their ionic functionality into three main types: (i) anion-conductive (ionomeric) binders, (ii) inert binders and (iii) mixed anion- and cation-conductive binders.

The first group is characterised by presence of quaternary ammonium, piperidinium, or imidazolium functional groups to facilitate hydroxide ion conduction within the CL. As a main commercial representatives FAA-3, PiperION, Sustanion, and Aemion can be mentioned. Presence of functional groups is essential for establishing effective triple-phase boundaries and ensuring continuous ionic pathways between the membrane and catalyst sites in environment of low ionic conductivity.

In contrast, the second group of non-conductive (inert) binders like PTFE, lacks ionic functionality, relying thus on sufficient ionic conductivity of the circulating electrolyte. As these materials are ionically inert, they are characterised by high mechanical and chemical stability thus providing critical mechanical support and improving CL structural stability. They are particularly useful in CCS-type MEAs and in environments where ionic conductivity is secured by liquid electrolyte [11].

Finally, the third group of mixed-functionality binders integrate both anion- and cation-conductive components. These hybrid systems aim to improve polymer binder cohesion and overall, MEA durability.

Most of the high-performance anion exchange ionomers are based on non-fluorinated, fully aromatic hydrocarbon backbones, particularly polymers such as poly(phenylene oxide) (PPO), poly(arylene ether), and more advanced poly(phenylene) or poly(aryl piperidinium) architectures. These structures offer enhanced thermal and chemical stability compared to older designs containing ether or benzylic linkages. They are prone to nucleophilic attack under alkaline conditions [12, 13]. The fully aromatic backbone is a crucial advancement in ionomer design. For instance, PAP-TP-85 and PiperION use poly(aryl piperidinium) structures in which the cationic piperidinium groups are tethered directly within the backbone. This configuration not only improves mechanical robustness and ionic conductivity but also substantially extends the operational lifetime in concentrated KOH solutions at elevated temperatures [14, 15]. In contrast, earlier-generation ionomers like FAA-3 or Aemion use side-chain tethered quaternary ammonium (NR_3^+) groups, which, while functional, are more susceptible to Hofmann elimination or nucleophilic substitution over time [6, 9, 10, 16].

The cationic groups embedded in these polymers such as quaternary ammonium, imidazolium and piperidinium also impact stability and conductivity. Piperidinium groups have become prominent due to their cyclic, sterically protected structures, which offer better alkaline tolerance than traditional linear quaternary ammonium groups. Similarly, multi-quaternized

variants such as PAP-TP-85-MQN demonstrate higher ion exchange capacities (IEC) and superior ionic conductivity due to increased density of fixed cationic sites [15].

Structural Trends in Non-Commercial Ionomers for AMWE

The growing complexity and performance demand of AMWE systems have catalysed the development of innovative polymer ionomers. In contrast to commercially available ones, these research-grade polymers allow for precise tuning of structural and functional properties and are typically paired with experimental membranes in custom MEA configurations. Though limited, recent research on non-commercial binders reveals structural trends, which will be discussed later in detail. Structurally, polymers used as binders can be roughly divided into block copolymers [17-19] or cross-linked polymers [20, 21].

Figure 1: Representative structures of non-commercial polymer binders AMWE. **Composite materials** – SEBS-DABCO with PIM (a) [18], **Fluorinated polymers** – quaternization of the poly(carbazole)-based polymer with Nafion (b) [4]; quaternized Poly(DMAEMA-co-TFEMA-co-BMA) (c) [22]; **Piperidine-based polymers** – poly(terphenyl piperidinium) containing hydrophilic crown ether units (d) [23], **triblock copolymer** incorporating N-methylpiperidinium and hydrophobic segments (e) [24]; **Cross-linked polymers** (f,g); quaternary ammonium grafted poly(vinyl benzyl chloride) based ionomer (f) [21], cross-linking of poly(norbornene) (g) [20].

Current trends in ionomer synthesis

Current key design trend in ionomer synthesis involves the use of fully aromatic, ether-free backbones resisting to alkaline degradation and offering stable ionic pathways. For instance, PFPB-QA, a quaternized polyfluorene-co-biphenyl ionomer with propyl spacers, achieves a high conductivity of 122 mS cm^{-1} at 80°C and supports current densities up to 1.53 A cm^{-2} at 2.0 V in 1 M KOH (70°C) when employed in a CCM configuration. The ionomer is matched with a chemically identical PFPB-QA membrane, ensuring excellent interfacial compatibility and stability [25].

Considering the role of the functional group, noteworthy innovative binder trend represents piperidinium-based ionomer development. These ionomers feature alkali-stable N,N-dimethylpiperidinium (DMP) cations directly incorporated into polyterphenyl backbone with enhanced water uptake and ion-dipole interactions for improved hydroxide transport. The series of poly(dibenzobenzyl-co-terphenyl piperidinium copolymers demonstrate promising conductivity up to 110 mS cm^{-1} at 80°C . Used as a binder in both CCM- and CCS-type MEAs, optimized ionomer enabled AMWE performance up to 2.0 A cm^{-2} at 2.1 V (80°C , 1 M NaOH). This design highlights the potential of combining cyclic cations and crown ether motifs, both incorporated inside the main chain for simultaneously enhancing conductivity and stability in alkaline environments [23].

Besides the synthesis itself, interesting way to tune the properties of the ionomers represents water uptake control [20]. This can be done by several approaches. Recent study introduced a triblock copolymer exploring the impact of hydrophobic block length on performance and durability. By adjusting the polyethylene content, the authors tuned water uptake (23–154%) and carbonate conductivity ($8\text{--}94 \text{ mS cm}^{-1}$ at 50°C). The conductivity and performance of the ionomer were mainly influenced by PE block content. Increased content of PE increased water uptake and consequently ionic conductivity. At the same time, however, the degradation rate was increased [24].

Originally, trimethylammonium functional groups were considered as the most stable functionally groups due to the missing beta-hydrogen atom, which prevents the Hoffman elimination reaction. Today's functional groups often yield their stability from their conformation of high flexibility or the polymer chain bearing functional group. As a backbone polymer chain, block copolymers, like styrene-ethylene-butylene-styrene, attracts lot of attention due to their ability to create domain microstructure, which helps to control swelling and achieve high ionic conductivity.

Specifics of the ionomers for application in catalyst layer

Several specific properties of the polymer binders must be taken into account when new materials are designed. For example, high accessibility of the reaction centres in the CL must be ensured. This effect is documented by SEBS-DABCO + PIM blend application in CCM-MEA approach. SEBS-DABCO (Figure 1a) serves as the hydroxide-conductive matrix. At the same time PIM, a polymer of intrinsic microporosity, enhances mass transport by increasing water and gas permeability. CL prepared with SEBS-DABCO + PIM, demonstrates electron conductivity in the range of $0.013\text{--}0.12 \text{ mS cm}^{-1}$ and total conductivity from 0.023 to 13.30 mS cm^{-1} , depending on the SEBS-DABCO/PIM – ratio. Whereas the conductivity of the CL is the highest for SEBS-DABCO binder without PIM, the best performance under operating conditions of the AMWE demonstrated 50% SEBS-DABCO/50% PIM ionomer. It is due to the improved mass-transport in the CL [18].

Accessibility of the reaction centres can also be influenced by affinity of the polymer binder to the catalyst. Ionomers such as QPC-TMA showcase the trade-offs associated with sterically hindered cationic groups (Figure 1b) allowing them to achieve high ionic conductivity (160 mS cm^{-1} at 80°C). Despite high ionic conductivity, it suffers from poor interfacial adhesion, particularly to IrO_2 catalysts. When blended with Nafion, improved binder cohesion as well as increased durability of MEA was achieved, highlighting the potential of composite systems [4].

Available literature indicates the specific interactions between polymer binder and catalyst particles to represent an important aspect. However, so far, this issue is not adequately understood.

Application of ionomers for AMWE with demineralised water

A highly important, but still unsolved field of AMWE is development of the materials for the operation with demineralized water as a circulating medium. For example, quaternized copolymer of polymethacrylate monomers exhibits a conductivity of 59 mS cm^{-1} at $50 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, along with robust mechanical properties (tensile strength $\sim 7.6 \text{ MPa}$, elongation 45.8%). Applied in a CCM MEA using a radiation-grafted membrane, it achieved 0.1 A cm^{-2} at 1.9 V under deionized water feed at room temperature. Its modular composition and processability make it a promising platform for further binder optimization [26].

To conclude this chapter, both, the commercial and innovative binders often originate from similar polymer classes—such as poly(phenylene oxide), polyaromatic hydrocarbons, and block copolymers—and face common challenges like alkaline degradation. Innovative variants under development, however, with increasing frequency adopt experimental architectures like functional groups with conformation protecting them from Hofmann elimination reaction, or polymer backbone chains allowing for the phase separation and domain microstructure formation. Such materials, often with tuneable compositions, can reach improved properties due to structure–property relationships.

Catalyst layers in AMWE

In comparison with the PGM-free catalyst, PGM catalysts can achieve higher current densities because of their higher catalytic activity (see Figure 2a). From PGM catalysts, IrO_2 and Pt are commonly applied to the anode and cathode, respectively [7, 8, 27]. However, due to the costs reason, PGM-free catalysts represent preferred option. Transition metal oxides, phosphides and alloys, such as NiFe_2O_4 , NiCo_2O_4 , NiMoO_4 , CoFeO_x , CoO_x , $\text{Cu}_x\text{Co}_x\text{O}_x$ or NiCoP , represent especially promising option for alkaline water electrolysis, [9, 19, 21, 28-31]. Due to different electrochemical activity, PGM and PGM-free catalysts will be presented separately in the figures.

This chapter focus on the comparison of the identified important parameters of the CL deposition, specifically catalyst to binder ratio (CBR), catalyst load and comparison between CCM and CCS approach for MEA fabrication.

Effect of catalyst to binder ratio

The influence of CBR for both CCM and CCS-MEAs was evaluated based on the literature data of current density achieved at cell voltage of 2 V . As expected, due to the lack of standardized experimental conditions, the data reported in literature were, unfortunately, obtained at different conditions (KOH concentrations, temperatures, etc.), which limits possibility of direct results comparison.

General trend of the CBR with PGM-free catalysts was investigated by Plevova et al. As it was observed, better performance under AMWE is achieved with increasing CBR (higher catalyst content in the CL) [19]. It was also shown that lower CBR (higher content of ionomer) increases total conductivity, while decreasing the electron conductivity of the CL. Electron conductivity

decrease was addressed to the encapsulation of the catalyst particles by electrically non-conductive ionomer [19].

Effect of CBR on water electrolysis performance was also studied by Koch et al. [8] with PGM catalysts. In agreement with Plevová et al [19], it was found, that CBR 93/7 represents the best compromise between electrolyzer performance and long-term durability). While the effect of CBR on the cathode side had no significant effect, changing CBR on the anode in range from 85/15 to 96/4 affected the electrolysis performance. Positive effect of high CBR (95/5) was confirmed also by Chen et al. [32]. Achieving the optimal performance frequently with high CBR could indicate that in these cases, electron conductivity of the CL represents performance limiting parameter.

Despite the fact the above-mentioned works showed similar optimal CBR values, this cannot be defined generally as it depends on the specific interactions between ionomer and catalyst.

Literature reveals, that performance of the AMWE can achieve PEM-like performance (current densities 4.8 A cm^{-2} at cell voltage 2 V) [27]. Such result was achieved with CCM-MEA containing PGM catalysts, specifically IrO_2 anode with CBR 95/5 and Pt-C 75/25 cathode. The MEA was tested with 1 mol dm^{-3} KOH liquid electrolyte and at a temperature of $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [27]. Current densities were shown to range from 3.31 A cm^{-2} to 4.8 A cm^{-2} at 2 V while modifying the CBR in the cathodic CL (CBR from 65/35 to 90/10 tested).

However, in the work of Faid et al. [29] high current density of 1.15 A cm^{-2} at 2 V, temperature $50 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ with 1 mol dm^{-3} KOH liquid electrolyte was achieved with CBR 80/20 on the both electrodes and $\text{Ni}_{0.6}\text{Co}_2\text{Fe}_{0.2}$ and Ni-MoO_2 on the anode and cathode. Comparison of the above works by Ma et al. [27] and Faid et al. [29] shows that optimal CBRs can be different for different catalyst and ionomer combination.

Literature survey on CBR (shown in Figure 2a) shows that quite wide range of CBR from 40 to 97 wt.% of catalyst was used. The best performances are typically achieved around 90 wt.% of catalyst in the CL for PGM catalysts and in the range 70–90 wt.% for PGM-free catalysts. Optimum range for CBR is given by the number of the triple-phase boundaries established within CL.

From the above review follows, that prevailing number of studies utilizes ionomer loading of 10 wt.% and lower. This seems to be connected with the undesired interaction of the ionomer with the catalyst. In selected cases it was found preferable to use different ionomer loading on anode and cathode side of the cell, which underlines specificity of interaction of ionomer with catalyst.

Figure 2: (A) Effect of CBR on current density at 2 V. and (B) effect of the catalyst load. Orange circle: PGM catalysts; Blue square: PGM-free catalysts

Effect of catalyst loading

In the traditional understanding, higher catalyst loading provides more active sites, thus accelerating electrode's reaction. On the other hand, however, it increases thickness of the CL. This can have two negative consequences. Firstly, higher CL thickness means potentially higher ohmic resistance. This was observed by Kreider et al. [33], who used catalysts with low conductivity (NiFe_2O_4 and Co_3O_4) and observed minimum effect of increasing loading on the MEA performance.

Secondly, in the case of electrical and ionic conductivities of the CL high enough, the reaction takes place predominantly at the CL and polymer membrane interface. Produced gaseous phase thus must penetrate through the entire thickness of the CL. If it is too high, pressure of the gaseous phase at interface will increase resulting potentially in CL delamination. Even if the delamination does not occur, increased pressure of the gaseous phase close to the anion exchange membrane utilized as separator of the electrode compartments will increase gas cross-over.

The loading is dependent on the type of catalyst – usually lower loadings are being used for the PGMs (see Figure 2b) as their price represents limiting parameter. On the other hand, due to its activity, low catalyst load is still enough to achieve high performance. According to the data reported in literature, the loading of PGM catalysts is almost exclusively under 5 mg cm^{-2} . For example, Chen et. al [32] discuss effect of catalyst loading on the CCM anode, resulting in finding the optimum loading of 2.2 mg cm^{-2} for Ir black.

Loading of PGM-free catalyst may range up to 20 mg cm^{-2} [34], see Figure 2b. As it is visible, increasing the catalyst amount in the CL above 5 mg cm^{-2} does not have a positive effect on the electrolysis performance. This is in agreement with the discussion of the CL thickness.

Figure 3: Comparison of current densities achieved with CCM- and CCS-MEA.

Effect of the catalyst layer substrate

Although CCM is commonly used for PEM fuel cells and water electrolyzers, in AMWE such approach is not yet well-established. This is due to several reasons. Firstly, anion selective polymer binders stable and efficient under conditions of AMWE are still under investigation. Another reason consists in the deposition methods of the CL, including often high-temperature step, which may lead to degradation of the anion selective membrane, e.g. hot-pressing. The CCM technique is investigated due to the better ionic contact between catalyst powder and polymer binder (ion conductor), which makes possible for diluted KOH solution or even pure water to be used as circulating electrolyte.

As shown in Figure 3, the current densities achieved by both MEA types are comparable or slightly higher with CCM-MEAs. However, CCM-MEAs achieved high current densities mostly using PGM catalysts having typically better catalytic properties (see Figure 3). It seems to be caused primarily by lower electronic conductivity of the PGM-free catalysts. For low conductivity catalysts, substrate used at CCS provides better electronic contact and charge distribution.

Conclusion

This short review confirms, that, despite significant advancement achieved in the field of alkaline polymer electrolyte membranes recently, development of ionomers serving as binders in CL represents still open field of research. It is mainly because application of the ionomers in the CL possesses additional demands on the polymer used. Besides others, corresponding affinity to the catalyst particles, to the membrane may be mentioned as examples. The currently followed trends may be summarised as utilization of hybrid systems, which combine polymers of different natures and tuning the properties of the ionomers via hydrophobic parts. However, relatively low number of the published studies, as well as a lack of standardization in developed ionomer testing prevent more detailed analysis and more precise conclusions. Instead, it may be stated, that intensive research in the field of new ionomers satisfying significant demands represents a crucial prerequisite to allow design of new generation the AMWE cell.

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Literature

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This paper offers a valuable insight into structure-property-performance relationship critical to advancing AEM electrolysis technology. It systematically investigates and optimizes the anion-selective ionomer structure, ionomer content in catalyst layer and electrode architecture. A hybrid membrane electrode assembly combining CCS anode and CCM cathode is presented.

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